

A study of the relationship between the Ethical Climate and the Organizational citizenship Behavior.

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Sabikeh Neghabi, ⁽²⁾Mahmood Ghorbani

Department of Education Management, Islamic Azad University, Bujnourd Branch, Iran. Corresponding Author: Sabikeh Neghabi, Master's Degree in Education Management Order of Authors: Sabikeh Neghabi, Mahmood Ghorbani

Abstract—This research has been carried out; with the objectives of identifying the relationship between the Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior of the employees within the Ministry of Education headquarter in the north Khurasan province. In this study, the relationship between six dimensions of Ethical Climate and Organizational Citizenship Behavior were reviewed. In order to evaluate these elements, from the sample of 200 people, through random test of all categories, results from 127 employees were obtained. A sample questionnaire was used for the final evaluation, by applying the Kronbach alpha, rendering the results more credible by the application of the aforementioned tool, in such a way that the alfa kronbach of the Ethical Climate questionnaire stood at 0.832% and the alpha Kronbach of the questionnaire on Organizational Citizenship Behavior stood at 0.637%. The findings have indicated that the Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior are correlated. Similarly, the Ethical tool value has the least correlation with the Organizational citizenship Behavior and the independent Ethical Climate has no connection with the Organizational citizenship Behavior.

Keywords— Ethical Climate, Organizational citizenship Behavior, Ethical tool value, Independent Ethical Climate.

I. INTRODUCTION

The new organizations are fundamentally different from their predecessors, from human resource, financial, technical level, field of activity, and management style point of view and their human resource, in various dimensions have been scrutinized.

In competitive world of today, all the organizations are perpetually seeking to find new ways to maximize their efforts and that of their employees. The development of new technology and the process of global economic expansion, to a greater extent, have contributed to a progressive competitiveness and inevitable changes in nature of the organizational structure and their employees. Furthermore, for the purpose of compatibility at the world

stage, satisfying the customer needs and their expectations, and adapting themselves to the ever-changing business environment, constantly, are on the lookout for more capable employees to render services beyond their job descriptions.

This type of employee behavior has dramatic effect on the compatibility of the company, so much so that this issue has attracted a great deal of attention among the researchers and business managers, alike. In the past, the researchers, in the process of reviewing the relationship between the Occupational Behavior and Organizational Effectiveness, they concentrated their effort mainly on the In-role Performance role of the employees. The internal role of the employees is applied to all those occupational behavior that has been defined in the related job description and official role of the organization that the system recognizes and is able to reward. For the last six decades, the researchers have drawn lines between the In-role Performance and Extra-role Performance of the

employees. The Extra-role Performance of the employees is considered to be beyond the official duties that have been clearly identified by the organization. Such behaviors are considered as voluntary and usually are not covered by the existing official reward system. The employees, in such circumstances, are not duty bound to render any services, however, the individual's reaction goes back to their organizational civility (Ackfeldt and Coote,2005).

The concept of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior has been the subject of many studies in the last 15 years, the importance of which seem to increase as the time goes by.

Considering the vital contributions of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior to the effectiveness of the organizations, the creation of such behavior, remains to be one of the important challenges of the managers. The creation of the Organizational citizenship Behavior, as a voluntary undertaking by the employee leads ultimately to the organizational prosperity.

In spite of advancement of information technology, there is an existing gap between the activities and effectiveness of the organization. There is a strong universal belief that the activities and effectiveness of the company, to a great extent, relates to the activities of the employees, beyond their actual job description.

One of the elements that could pave the ground for the blossoming of the Organizational Citizenship Behavior, is the Ethic. Business Ethics, gained a momentum in literature of Ethic, in early 1990s and various aspects of it in different variety of forms were scrutinized by the academics. Today, with the ever increasing complexity of the organizations, rampant unethical and unlawful behavior within the working environment, the need to introduce an Ethical Climate is now greater than ever.

Every organization, even superficially, appear to abide by all the values and standards of ethics without taking a

detour from its principles. The employees of every organization are considered as the most fundamental part of its entity, acting as the determining factor in adherence to all the ethical principles.

Acknowledging the vital role of ethics in organizational success, the organizational ethical charter and its code of conduct, have become the yardstick to establish and measure all the strategic decisions in order to standardize the daily behavioral pattern of all the employees.

Beside the necessity of having a set of clearly defined rules and regulations (that define the behavior limits), the codes and ethical principles (that the organizations enforce it on the employees), there are variety of other elements that affect the ethical behavior of the employees. One of those elements that has had substantial effect on the behavior of the individuals, is the Ethical Climate, about which a great deal of research has been carried out.

The Ethical Climate has psychological structure, derived from a collection of individual perception. In other words, it is applied to an established, common and meaningful understanding that the employees harbor in regards to the existing ethical and strategic matters with the organizations. Therefore, the Ethical Climate, relates to one of those climates that reflects the patterns, policies and the activities of the organization, with an ethical result e been made(Filipova,2007).

As a result, in this study, efforts have been made to review the Ethical Climate and its relationship with the Organizational Citizenship Behaviour.

The theory of Ethical Climate (ECT), is one of those structures that logically is one of the most effective original concept in the field of Business Ethics (Martin and Cullen, 2006).

The Ethical Climate of an organization, is an indispensable source of information for the employees to guide them through rights and wrongs of the ethical matters (Shafer, 2008).

Bulutlar and Oz (2009), stress that there are variety of climates are present within the working environment, one of which is the Ethical Climate that relate to norm systems of the organizations.

The concept of Ethical Climate is similar to other climates like Organizational Climate or organizational cultures and Spirituality, however, more than any of them, concentrates on the issues of Ethics and Spirituality (shafer,2008).

In the second half of 1980s, Victor and Cullen, went about presenting a structure for measuring the Ethical Climates of the working environment. By following Eshnaider's research on working climate, they managed to systematize their research on norm systems of the working place. These systems, in line with precise reflection of the working climate, according to Eshnaider, should become systematized and the employees must understand the

norms that are clearly identifiable and reliable (Webber,2007:570).

Victor and Cullen's Ethical climate is a collection of general outstanding features of the organization that affects a widespread decision making prism of the organization that we consider as the culture of the organization. They argue that, the individual characteristics are insufficient to explain or forecast the ethical behavior. This research focuses on type identification of two dimensional ethical spaces.

The first dimension relates to the ethical benchmark, taking into account three major theoretical classifications of Self-Centerism, Utilitarianism, and Deontology.

The second dimension, relates to the focus of dispersion and application of the analysis for publicizing the ethical benchmarks in individual prism, local (organization, division and the working group) and at cosmopolitan level. This dimension, identifies the source of ethical reasoning that is used in ethical benchmarking for organizational decision making process or its limitations during the ethical analysis of such decisions (Victor and Cullen,1987: 55).

The axis of personal analysis, identifies the sources of ethical reasoning among the individuals and the local analysis identifies the sources of ethical reasoning at organizational level. The cosmopolitan axis deals with the ethical reasoning outside the organization. (Maesschalck,2005).

The combinations of these two dimensions create a matrix. In this matrix, every focal point is combined in order to establish an ethical climate. As a result nine different kinds of ethical climates are created. All the nine types of climates, provide adequate information about the understanding of the effect of the organizational behavior. The nine different types of climates are as follows: Personal interests (tool related), Organizational Interests (tool related), Effectiveness, Social responsibility, Team Interests, Friendship (looking after), Organizational Regulations and manners(laws), The codes of professional conducts and its related regulations and Personal manners(independent) (Debra and Sherril,2008).

TABLE I
VICTOR AND CULLEN ETHICAL CLIMATE FRAME
(DEBRA AND SHERRIL,2008).

The Center of Analysis			The ethical benchmark
Cosmopolitanism	Local	Personal	
Effectiveness	Organization interests	Personal interests	Selfishness
Social Responsibility	Team interests	friendship	Do-gooder attitude
Professional codes and regulations	Organizational regulations and manners	Personal manner	The ethical regulations

With the introduction of the Ethical Climate framework by Victor and Cullen (1987), the Ethical Climate research in fields of business and ethics grew rapidly. In the following years, after its introduction, experimental research has indicated a relationship between the ethical climate and a series of other events. These events do not only include ethic related differentials, but also the work results that often are found in relation to management and organizational research studies.(for instance the employee undertakings and work satisfaction). In addition, nowadays, there are many on-going researches to encompass other scientific fields, so that, it would include wider framework of ECT(Martin and Cullen,2006).

The Ethical Climate structure of Victor and Cullen's argument(1987) is quite powerful, so much so that, by application of the Ethical Climate Questionnaire(ECQ), the validity of most researchers are evaluated.

Although, for the first time the terminology of "Organizational Citizenship Behavior" was applied by Oregan ,et al in 1983, nevertheless, others like Ketz and Kahn stressed the distinction between the activities, role and Innovative and spontaneous behaviors in 1970s and 1980s, and Chester Barnard before them by stating the concept of willingness to cooperate in 1938 (podsakoff, et al 2000:513).

Oregan considers the Citizenship Behavior of the employees, as positive actions that some employees take, in order to improve the efficiency level, fraternity and unity at work that is beyond the organizational responsibility.

Some researchers like Graham, suggests that Organizational Citizenship Behavior, must be separated from general flow of work. Through this vision, the Organizational Citizenship Behavior must be addressed as a global issue, which takes all the positive behaviors of the organization into account (Castro and Ruiz, 2004).

The Organizational Citizenship Behavior was defined Oregan in 1998 as:

The behavior that is based on individual whim and willingness, without being clearly defined, expected, or rewarded by the organization, directly or otherwise. Nevertheless, such behavior leads to better activities and ultimate effectiveness of the organization(Markoczy and Xin, 2004:1).

Bolino and Turnley (2003) believe that Citizenship behavior envelop two general characteristics: they can't be directly influenced or improved. For instance, from technical point of view, they can't be included in individuals workload and in addition, they are the product of the extraordinary voluntary contributions that many organizations have come to depend on for their eventual success(Bolino and Turnley, 2003).

The following are the elements that affect the Organizational Citizenship Behavior:

The encompassing analysis of the connection between the Organizational Citizenship Behavior and the affecting elements, suggest that in fact four distinct categories that have been the focus of the research:

Employees' outstanding individual characteristics

Outstanding characteristics of the job

Outstanding Characteristics of the organization

Outstanding Characteristics of the Leadership (Podsakoff, et al, 2000:526).

For the purpose of identifying the scientific value of the research and attaining the recognition in line with theoretical origin of the research, we set about to review its history. The previous results of all the researches indicate, that variety of studies have been carried out on the relationship between the ethical climate and the organizational citizenship behavior.

Heidari,et al(2012), in his study of reviewing the understanding of the nurses about the connection between ethical climate and their moral behavior in the hospitals of the University of Medical Science in Mashad (Iran), concluded that here is a meaningful connections between the understanding of the nurses in regards to the dimensions of personal interests, the ethical climate (selfishness-individualist attitude) and their immoral behavior. The findings of this study indicated that the understanding of the nurses from the ethical climate of the hospital is mostly based on ethical principles and do-gooder attitude with limited degree of selfishness and from analytical point of view, it is mostly individualistic.

Taripesid(2002) studied the connectivity of organizational ethical behavior and personal manner, and went on to conclude that as a Good Soldier Syndrome in organizational citizenship behavior, the behavior of the soldiers could be considered as moral or immoral and goes on to say that The pillars of this kind of behavior is based on ethics an higher moral standard leads to a higher organizational citizenship behavior.

Sokes, et al(1996) in a study of the connections between the working mentality, occupational outlook, and quitting the work among the employees of the service industry, concluded that There is a relationship between having a strong work ethics, work satisfaction and the organizational responsibility and in an indirect manner with the desire for quitting the work.

From what has already been said and the emphasis on the importance of organizational ethics, the ethical issues, must be addressed as a necessity among the organizations in Iran.

II. THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The selected community for this study, encapsulates the entire 200 employees of the Headquarter of the Education Office in the North Khurasan province. The number of the research sample, by applying Curtsy Morgan table, has been determined to be 127 individuals, to render a meaningful result from that group. A questionnaire has been used to acquire the required information, and for this purpose the ethical climate questionnaire of Victor and Cullen (1987) and the organizational citizenship behavior questionnaire of Oregon and Kanoski (1996) were used.

TABLE II

THE SIZE OF ALPHA KRONBACH FOR THE ETHICAL CLIMATE QUESTIONNAIRE

Alpha Chronbach Ratio	No of questions
0.832	26

For the Organizational Citizenship Behavior questionnaire, the value of 0.637 for the alpha konbach ratio of the questionnaire was also obtained.

TABLE III

SHOWS THE VALUE OF ALPHA CRONBACH RATIO FOR THE ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR QUESTIONNAIRE

Alpha Kronbach Ratio	No of questions
0.637	15

For reviewing the existence of correlation between the research variables, Pearson correlation was used.

III FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

1-The result that was obtained from the main hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) shows that the correlation value of these differentials is 0.447. Therefore, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 > 0.000$, the existence of a relationship between these two differentials is acceptable, and the correlation value of 0.447, indicates that there is a positive relationship between these two variables.

TABLE IV

THE RESULTS OF THE PEARSON’S CORRELATION TEST FOR THE MAIN HYPOTHESIS

Organizational Citizenship Behavior		The Variable	
***0.447	Correlation Coefficient	The Ethical Climate	The main hypothesis
0.000	Meaningful Level		
127	Sample Size		

2- The result that was obtained from the first secondary hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Caring Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) indicates that the correlation value of these variables is 0.459 Hence, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 > 0.000$, the existence of a relationship between these two differentials is acceptable, and the correlation value of 0.459, indicates that there is a positive relationship between these two variables.

TABLE V

THE RESULTS OF THE CORRELATION TEST OF PEARSON FOR THE FIRST SECONDARY HYPOTHESIS

Organizational Citizenship Behavior		Variable	
***0.459	Correlation Coefficient	Caring Ethical Climate	The first secondary hypothesis
0.000	The meaningful level		
127	Sample size		

3 -The result that was obtained from the second secondary hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Regulatory Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) indicates that the correlation value of these variables is 0.567 Hence, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 > 0.000$, the existence of a relationship between these two differentials is acceptable, and the correlation value of 0.567, indicates that there is a positive relationship between these two variables.

TABLE VI

THE RESULTS OF PEARSON CORRELATION TEST FOR THE SECOND SECONDARY HYPOTHESIS

Organizational Citizenship behavior		The Variable	
***0.567	Correlation Coefficient	Regulatory Ethical climate	The second secondary hypothesis
0.000	Meaningful level		
127	Sample size		

4-The result that was obtained from the third secondary hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Regulatory Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) indicates that the correlation value of these variables is 0.476 Hence, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 > 0.000$, the existence of a relationship between these two differentials is acceptable, and the correlation value of 0.476, indicates that there is a positive relationship between these two variables.

TABLE VII

THE RESULTS OF PEARSON'S CORRELATION TEST FOR THE THIRD SECONDARY HYPOTHESIS

Organizational Citizenship Behavior		The variable	
***0.467	The Correlation Coefficient	The regulations	The third secondary hypothesis
0.000	The meaningful Level		
127	Sample size		

5- The result that was obtained from the fourth secondary hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Tool Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) indicates that the correlation value of these variables is 0.226 Hence, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 > 0.011$, the existence of a relationship between these two differentials is acceptable, and the correlation value of 0.226, indicates that there is a weak relationship between these two variables.

TABLE IX

THE RESULTS OF PEARSON'S CORRELATION TEST FOR THE FOURTH SECONDARY HYPOTHESIS

The Organizational Citizenship Behavior		The Variable	
***0.226	The Correlation Coefficient	The Tool Ethical climate	The fourth secondary Hypothesis
0.011	The Meaningful Level		
	Sample Size		

6.The result that was obtained from the fifth secondary hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Efficiency Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) indicates that the correlation value of these variables is 0.486 Hence, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 > 0.000$, the existence of a relationship between these two differentials is acceptable, and the correlation value of 0.486, indicates that there is a positive relationship between these two variables.

TABLE X

THE RESULTS OF PEARSON'S CORRELATION TEST FOR THE FIFTH SECONDARY HYPOTHESIS

Organizational Citizenship Behavior		The Variable	
***0.486	The Correlation Coefficient	Efficiency Ethical climate	The fifth secondary hypothesis
0.000	The Meaningful Level		
127	Sample size		

7-The result that was obtained from the sixth secondary hypothesis (there is a relationship between the Independent Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior) indicates that the correlation value of these variables is 0.059 Hence, by taking into account that the meaningful level value is at $0.05 < 0.512$, the existence of a relationship between these two variables is unacceptable.

TABLE XI
THE RESULTS OF PEARSON'S CORRELATION TEST
FOR THE SIXTH SECONDARY HYPOTHESIS

The Organizational Citizenship Behavior		The Variable	
0.059	The Correlation Coefficient	The independent Ethical Climate	The sixth secondary Hypothesis
0.512	The Meaningful Level		
127	Sample size		

officials should endeavor to create an organizational climate in line to increase teamwork among the employees by reducing the unhealthy competition, self-interest and the tool ethical climate.

- The outcome of the fifth secondary hypothesis indicates that there is a relationship between the efficiency ethical climate and the organizational citizenship behavior. The officials of the education department should head the findings of this study and implement the professional and the legal standards in order to improve the efficiency ethical climate.
- The result of the sixth secondary hypothesis indicates that there is no relationship between the independent ethical climate and organizational citizenship behavior. Hence, it is suggested that the education officials induce the background of unity and partnership through work training and workshop in order to eliminate independent ethical climate and the self-interest.

IV THE CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS, BASED ON THE FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

- Due to the findings of the main hypothesis, indicating that there is a correlation between the Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior, it is suggest that the education officials, in order to improve The Organizational Citizenship Behavior, must seriously address the Ethical climate issue and its related charter.
- Considering the findings of the research from the first secondary hypothesis, that there is relationship between the Caring Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship Behavior; it is suggested that the education officials ought to respect the views of the employees, in order to prepare the ground for a unified decision making process, safeguard and improve the caring ethical climate.
- By taking into account the results of the second secondary hypothesis, that there a correlation between the Regulatory Ethical Climate and the Organizational Citizenship behavior, it is proposed that the education officials to clarify the strategy and the work regulations of the organization and let go of the inflexible attitude, in order to safeguard and improve the organizational ethical climate.
- Reflecting the outcome of the study of the third secondary hypothesis, that there is a correlation between the regulatory ethical climate and the organizational citizenship, it is suggested that for the purpose of safeguarding and improving the regulatory ethical climate, the organizational regulations be thoroughly implemented, removing any possible doubts about the controlling of the ethical occasions.
- The study of the outcome of the fourth secondary hypothesis shows that there is weak link between the tool ethical climate and the organizational citizenship behavior. Therefore, it is suggested that the education

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